

‘New Methods to Solve some Types of the First Order D.E.s .’

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Abstract:- There are six Rules to solve the non exact differential equations (D.E.s) so we must learn and keep them and choose the proper Rule to find the Integrating Factor [$\mu(x,y)$] of the D.E. . so we must multiply I.F. by the equation to make it an exact and then integrate it , but sometimes this takes long time , more paper and more mistakes .There are two types of the first order differential equations either an exact or non exact and the exact D.E. can solved (integrated) directly but for non exact we must find the integrating factor $\mu(x,y)$. The exact D.E. usually is the derivative of a function of one or many functions each one of them is linear and independent on the others.

But if one function or more are rational or logarithmic so the D.E. becomes non exact.

For me I discovered new methods to find the

integrating factor in one procedure to solve many types of the differential equations of the first order in short time with simple ways (may be without integration) and this will increase the FLEXIBILITY to choose the simple and short procedure.

There are two types of the non exact differential equations can not solved by my method :

- 1 . The homogeneous D.E. which contents the same term in M & N together .
- 2 . The editing D.E. which we can not find the right integrating factor of it from M and N .

Keywords:- By checking most of the D.E.s so you may write at least one of its functions directly without integration then from that function you can calculate the integrating factor Alsultani I. F. Simply .

1. INTRODUCTION

Referring to my old article intitled (New way to solve the first order linear D.E. which consists of three terms) we find:

$$ax^m y^n + bx^s = c_1 \text{ where } (a, b, c_1, m \text{ and } n) \text{ are constants} \quad [5]$$

when differentiating it w.r. to x we find

$$anx^m y^{n-1} dy + amx^{m-1} y^n dx + bsx^{s-1} dx = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{then } (amx^{m-1} y^n + bsx^{s-1}) dx + anx^m y^{n-1} dy = 0 \quad (2)$$

↑↑

Positive sign $M = (amx^{m-1} y^n + bsx^{s-1})$ and $N = anx^m y^{n-1}$ positive sign from ‘Equation (2)’ we find that :

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} = amnx^{m-1} y^{n-1} \text{ and } \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} = amnx^{m-1} y^{n-1} \text{ so } \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \text{ i.e. the D.E. is an exact}$$

so when dividing by the coefficient of (dy) we get

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{amy}{anx} = - \frac{bsx^{s-m-1}}{any^{n-1}} \quad (3)$$

then if we take the left side of ‘Equation (3) we can write

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{my}{nx} \rightarrow a \left(\frac{ndy}{y} + \frac{mdx}{x} \right) \rightarrow a \left(n \int \frac{dy}{y} + m \int \frac{dx}{x} \right) \rightarrow a(n \ln y + m \ln x) \rightarrow a e^{n \ln y + m \ln x} \rightarrow a x^m y^n \text{ so}$$

$$.f(x,y) = a x^m y^n \text{ without integration} \quad (4)$$

Then if in some D.E.s we can obtain the expression $\frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{my}{nx}$ that means we find separated function which it is a part of the all functions that differentiated previously.

So any D.E. is an exact but it is not if and only if there is one of the following causes :

- 1 . there is abbreviated (abstracted) variable from it .
- 2 . one of the functions or more is rational .
- 3 . one of the functions or more is logarithmic .

but if there is one function like ;

$$f(x,y) = a x^m y^n = c \text{ alone then when differentiate it w. r. to } x$$

$$Df(x, y) = \frac{df}{dx} + \frac{df}{dy} \frac{dy}{dx} \text{ so } Df(x, y) = anx^m y^{n-1} dy + amx^{m-1} y^n dx = 0$$

Then it is either the common factor = $ax^{m-1} y^{n-1} = 0$ or the rest of the D.E. i.e. $nx dy + my dx = 0$

Now if for example the whole function $F(x,y)=f(x,y) + g(x,y)$

So $f(x,y)=ax^m y^n$ and $g(x,y)=\frac{b}{x^s}$

Then $F(x,y)=ax^m y^n + \frac{b}{x^s}=c$ where (a, b and c) are arbitrary constants

so by the differentiation we get :

$$F' = anx^m y^{n-1} dy + amx^{m-1} y^n dx - \frac{bs dx}{x^{s+1}} = 0 \text{ then :}$$

$$.anx^{m+s+1} y^{n-1} dy + amx^{m+s} y^n dx - bs dx = 0 \text{ by ordering}$$

$$(amx^{m+s} y^n - bs) dx + anx^{m+s+1} y^{n-1} dy = 0 \text{ (5)}$$

$$M=amx^{m+s} y^n - bs \text{ and } N = anx^{m+s+1} y^{n-1}$$

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} = amnx^{m+s} y^{n-1} \text{ and } \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} = an(m+s+1)x^{m+s} y^{n-1}$$

So $\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \neq \frac{\partial N}{\partial x}$ and the D.E. becomes non exact

But from ‘‘Equation (5) we find that ‘‘

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{amx^{m+s} y^n}{anx^{m+s+1} y^{n-1}} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{my}{nx} \text{ so } f(x, y) = ax^m y^n \text{ as in ‘‘(4),’’ [here I separate the coefficient (a) alone]}$$

Now if we differentiate $f(x,y)$ partially w.r. to (y) for example we get

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(ax^m y^n)}{\partial y} = anx^m y^{n-1} \text{ then this result must equal the derivative}$$

$$(anx^{m+s-1} y^{n-1})$$

But it is not equal so there must be integrating factor $\mu(x,y)$

$$.anx^m y^{n-1} = \mu(anx^{m+s-1} y^{n-1}) \text{ then}$$

$$\mu = \frac{anx^m y^{n-1}}{anx^{m+s-1} y^{n-1}} = \frac{1}{x^{s+1}} \text{ I called this } \boxed{\text{Alsultani I. F.}}$$

and to proof that let

$$M_1 = \mu M = \frac{1}{x^{s+1}} (amx^{m+s} y^n - bs) = anx^{m-1} y^{n-1} + \frac{bs}{x^{s+1}}$$

$$\text{then } \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = amnx^{m-1} y^{n-1}$$

$$N_1 = \mu N = \frac{1}{x^{s+1}} (anx^{m+s+1} y^{n-1}) = anx^m y^{n-1} \text{ then } \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = amnx^{m-1} y^{n-1}$$

$$\frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} \text{ now an exact D.E. .}$$

$$\text{so } F(x,y)=f(x,y)+g(x,y)=ax^m y^n + \int \frac{-bs dx}{(x^{s+1})} + c = ax^m y^n + \frac{b}{x^s} + c \text{ solution}$$

From now to the end of the research I will deal with the D.E.s which consist of four or more terms only . types D.E.s

1. $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{my}{nx}$ then its solution (function) is $f = x^m y^n$
2. $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-my}{nx}$ then its solution (function) is $f = \frac{y^n}{x^m}$
3. $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{amy}{anx} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{my}{nx}$ then $f = ax^m y^n$
4. $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-amy}{anx} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{-my}{nx}$ then $f = a \frac{y^n}{x^m}$
5. $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2xy}{2x^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{2x}$ so either $f = x^2 y^2$ and its derivative = $2x^2 y dy + 2xy^2 dx$
 .or $f = 2xy$ and its derivative = $2x dy + 2y dx$ and this must be checked in M and N .

let us take the following cases :

• CASE 1.

$$F(x,y)=f(x,y)+g(x,y)+k(x,y)=c$$

Where $f(x,y)=ax^m y^n$, $g(x,y)=\frac{b}{x}$ and $k(x,y)=r \ln|y|$ where (a, b and r are constants)

$$F' = f' + g' + k'$$

$$F' = anx^m y^{n-1} dy + amx^{m-1} y^n dx - \frac{bdx}{x^2} + \frac{r dy}{y} = 0 \text{ (we see here that } \mu = \frac{1}{x^2 y} \text{)}$$

$$anx^{m+2} y^n dy + amx^{m+1} y^{n+1} dx - by dx + rx^2 dy = 0$$

$$(amx^{m+1}y^{n+1} - by)dx + (anx^{m+2}y^n + rx^2)dy = 0$$

↑ positive sign ↑ positive sign

$$.y(amx^{m+1}y^n - b)dx + x^2(anx^m y^n + r)dy = 0 \quad (\text{outside the brackets } y \text{ and } x^2)$$

And $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{ay(mx^{m+1}y^n)}{ax^2(nx^m y^n)} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + a \frac{my}{nx} \rightarrow \int df = a[\int \frac{ndy}{y} + \int \frac{mdx}{x}] = a[\ln y^n + \ln x^m] \quad f = a[e^{\ln y^n + x^m}] = ax^m y^n$ then $\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial a(x^m y^n)}{\partial y} = ax^m y^{n-1} = \mu[ax^2(nx^m y^n)]$ so $\mu = \frac{1}{x^2 y}$

Or $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-by}{rx^2} \rightarrow \frac{rdy}{y} + \frac{-bdx}{x^2} \rightarrow r \int \frac{dy}{y} - b \int \frac{dx}{x^2} = r \ln|y| + \frac{b}{x}$ and $\mu = \frac{1}{x^2 y}$

then $f = \frac{1}{x^2 y} \int (amx^{m+1}y^{n+1})dx = a x^m y^n$

$F = r \ln|y| + \frac{b}{x} + \int \frac{1}{x^2 y} (amx^{m+1}y^n)dx + c = r \ln y + \frac{b}{x} + ax^m y^n + c$ solution

• CASE 2.

But when $f(x,y) = \frac{1}{m} x^m y^m$ i.e. the multiplied factor = the powers of both of x and y

$F = \frac{1}{m} x^m y^m + \frac{b}{x} + r \ln|y|$ then

$F' = \frac{m}{m} x^m y^{m-1} dy + \frac{m}{m} x^{m-1} y^m dx - \frac{bdx}{x^2} + \frac{rdy}{y} = 0$

$(x^{m+1}y^{m+1} - by)dx + (x^{m+2}y^m + rx^2)dy = 0$

Or $y(x^{m+1}y^m - b)dx + x^2(x^m y^m + r)dy = 0$ (also here we see y and x^2 outside the brackets) so although we say that :

$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{x^{m+1}y^{m+1}}{x^{m+2}y^m} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{x}$ this result is not useful because this will tell us that $f=xy$

And its derivative + xdy + ydx which are not existing in M and N but from the experience since x^2 is found in the end of N and it is multiplied by dy then let

$.z=xy$ and $f = \frac{1}{m} (z)^m$ [here $(x^m = x^{2-1}$ for $x^2)dy$ and $(x^m = x^{3-1} = x^2$ for $x^3)dy$

and $x^m = x^{4-1} = x^3$ for $x^4)dy$.

But also we can take the right insides of the brackets

$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-by}{rx^2}$ and by separating the variables we get

$\frac{rdy}{y} + \frac{-bdx}{x^2}$ then $r \int \frac{dy}{y} - b \int \frac{dx}{x^2} \rightarrow r \ln|y| + \frac{b}{x}$ which are $g(x,y) + k(x,y)$

Also here $\mu = \frac{1}{x^2 y}$

$M_1 = \mu M = \frac{y}{x^2 y} (x^{m+1}y^{m+1} - b) = x^{m-1}y^m - bx^{-2}$

Then $\frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = x^{m-1}y^{m-1}$

$N_1 = \mu N = \frac{1}{x^2 y} a[x^2(x^m y^m + r)] = ax^m y^{m-1} + \frac{r}{y}$ then $\frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = ax^{m-1}y^{m-1}$

Then $\frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x}$ so becomes an exact

So $F = r \ln|y| + \frac{b}{x} + \int \frac{1}{x^2 y} (x^{m+1}y^{m+1})dx = r \ln y + \frac{b}{x} + \frac{1}{m} x^m y^m + c$ solution

Notes

The same as in case 1.

For example

$F = \frac{1}{3} x^3 y^3 + \frac{1}{x} + \ln|y| = c$

So $F' = x^3 y^{3-1} dy + x^{3-1} y^3 dx - \frac{dx}{x^2} + \frac{dy}{y} = 0$

$(x^4 y^4 - y)dx + (x^5 y^3 + x^2)dy = 0$ and

$y(x^4 y^3 - 1)dx + x^2(x^3 y^3 + 1)dy = 0$ also $\mu = \frac{1}{x^2 y}$

$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{x^4 y^4}{x^5 y^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{x}$ so $z = xy$ and $m = 4 - 1 = 3$ then $f = \frac{1}{m} z^m = \frac{1}{3} (xy)^3$

$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{x^2}$ and by separating the variables we get

$\frac{dy}{y} + \frac{-dx}{x^2}$ then $\int \frac{dy}{y} - \int \frac{dx}{x^2} \rightarrow \ln|y| + \frac{1}{x}$ which are $g(x,y) + k(x,y)$

$F = \ln|y| + \frac{1}{x} + \int \frac{1}{x^2 y} (x^4 y^4)dx = \ln y + \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{3} x^3 y^3 + c$ solution

$$N_1 = \mu N = xy(4xy^2 - 2x^3) = 4x^2y^3 - 2x^4y \text{ then } \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = 8xy^3 - 8x^3y$$

$$\frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} \text{ i.e. an exact}$$

$$F = \int (2xy^4 - 4x^3y^2)dx + c = x^2y^4 - x^4y^2 + c$$

$$\text{So } F(x,y) = f(x,y) + g(x,y) = x^2y^4 - x^4y^2 = x^2y^2(y^2 - x^2) = c$$

The problem may be solved as a homogeneous and

$$I.F. = \mu = \frac{1}{Mx + Ny} = \frac{1}{xy[y^2 - 2x^2 + 2y^2 - x^2]} = \frac{1}{3xy^3 - 3x^3y}$$

Or $y = vx$ and $dy = vdx + xdv$ so

$$\frac{dx}{x} = \frac{2v^2 - 1}{3(v^2 - v)} dv$$

The following differential equations can not solve by my new method ;

1) $(2x^2y^2 + y)dx - (x^3y - 3x)dy = 0$ because of

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2x^2y^2}{-x^3y} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{-x} \rightarrow f = \frac{-x}{y^2} \text{ and } \frac{\partial(-\frac{x}{y^2})}{\partial x} = \frac{-1}{y^2} = \mu_1(2x^2y^2) \text{ so } \mu_1 = \frac{1}{x^2y^4} \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{3x} \rightarrow g = xy^3 \text{ then } \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} = y^3 = \mu_2 \text{ i.e. } \mu_2 = \mu_1 \text{ so } \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$$

2) in some of the homogeneous D.E.s if there is one term or more in M and N in the same time like;

a) $(x^2 + y^2 - xy)dx - xydy = 0$ because we cannot say $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-xy}{-xy}$

b) $y^2dx + (x^2 + 3xy + 4y^2)dy = 0$ because we cannot say $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^2}{4y^2}$

We knew that the integration of the non exact differential equation is longer and harder than its differentiation because of the absence of the integrating factor.

Then I tried to find some methods to solve many differential equations directly by separating two of its terms to find their original function by logarithms without integrating the D.E. completely (function after function) and solving the other types by finding one function directly **without integration** and then obtaining the I.F. from it to complete the solution by integrations simply.

So I succeed

Main Results

from here to the end of the research I will deal with the D.E.s of four or more terms.

➤ **Example 1**

Solve

$$y(xy + 2y + 2)dx + (2xy + 5)dy = 0$$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y^2}{2xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{2x} \text{ so } g(x,y) = 2xy \text{ but not } (x^2y^2) \text{ because we have no its derivatives } 2y^2x dx +$$

$2x^2y dy$ in M and N respectively

$$\text{so } \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial(2xy)}{\partial x} = 2y = \mu(2xy) \text{ and } \mu = \frac{1}{y}$$

$$M_1 = \mu M = \frac{y(x+2y+2)}{y} = x + 2y + 2 \text{ so } \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = 2$$

$$N_1 = \mu N = \frac{1}{y}(2xy + 5) = 2x + \frac{5}{y} \text{ so } \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = 2 \text{ then } \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} \text{ i.e. an exact}$$

$$F = 2xy + \int \frac{1}{y}(xy^2 + 2y)dx + \int \frac{1}{y}(5dy) = \frac{x^2y}{2} + 2xy + 5 \ln|y| + c$$

By the old methods

$$x^\alpha y^\beta M \text{ and } x^\alpha y^\beta N \text{ then I.F.} = x^\alpha y^\beta \text{ so long method}$$

➤ **Example 2**

Integrate $(-3y^3 - x^2y)dx + (2xy^2 + x^4)dy = 0$

Solution

$$(-3y^3 - x^2y)dx + (2xy^2 + x^4)dy = 0$$

$$y(-3y^2 - x^2)dx + (2xy^2 + x^4)dy = 0$$

we see above μ consistsof y which is outside of M bracket and x^4 which is inside the N bracket $x^{2m-2} = x^{2(3)-2} = x^4$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y^3}{2xy^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y}{2x} \rightarrow f = \frac{y^2}{x^3}$$

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \frac{y^2}{x^3}}{\partial y} = \frac{2y}{x^3} = \mu(2xy^2) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{2y}{x^3(2xy^2)} = \frac{1}{x^4y}$$

$$M_1 = \mu M = \frac{1}{x^4y} (-3y^3 - x^2y) = \frac{-3y^2}{x^4} - \frac{1}{x^2} \text{ so } \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{-6y}{x^4}$$

$$N_1 = \mu N = \frac{1}{x^4y} (2xy^2 + x^4) = \frac{2y}{x^3} + \frac{1}{y} \text{ so } \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = \frac{-6y}{x^4} \text{ then } \frac{\partial M_1}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x}$$

$$F = \frac{y^2}{x^3} - \frac{1}{x^4y} \int x^2y dx + \frac{1}{x^4y} \int x^4 dy + c = \frac{y^2}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x} + \ln|y| + c \text{ solution}$$

Or $\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-yx^2}{x^4} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-yx^2}{x^4} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{y} + \frac{-x^2 dx}{x^4} \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4y}$

and $\frac{dy}{y} + \frac{-dx}{x^2} \rightarrow \ln|y| + \frac{1}{x}$

or the problem can solved as $I.F = x^\alpha y^\beta$

➤ Example 3

Solve $(y^4 + 2xy)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2)dy = 0$

Solution

$$(y^4 + 2xy)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2)dy = 0 \text{ eq. (1)}$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

↑↑

$$y(y^3 + 2x)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2)dy = 0 \text{ eq. (2)}$$

From eq. (2) we see that (y^3) exists inside the two brackets so $\mu = \frac{1}{y^3}$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^4}{xy^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{x} \text{ then } f(x,y) = xy$$

$$\frac{\partial f(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(xy)}{\partial y} = x \text{ then } x = \mu(xy^3) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

$$M_1 = \mu M = \mu = \frac{1}{y^3} [y(y^3 + 2xy)] = y - \frac{2x}{y^2}$$

$$\text{so } \frac{\partial}{\partial y} M_1 = 1 + \frac{4x}{y^3}$$

$$N_1 = \mu N = \frac{1}{y^3} (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2) = x - \frac{2}{y} - \frac{2x^2}{y^3}$$

$$\frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} = 1 - \frac{4x}{y^3}$$

$$F(x,y) = xy + \int \frac{1}{y^3} (2xy) dx + \int_{(y \text{ only})} \frac{1}{y^3} (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2) dy = xy + \frac{x^2}{y^2} + 2 \ln|y| = c \text{ End}$$

Another solution

$$(y^4 + 2xy)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2)dy = 0$$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2xy}{-2x^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{-2x} \rightarrow g(x,y) = \frac{x^2}{y^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \frac{x^2}{y^2}}{\partial x} = \frac{2x}{y^2} = \mu(2xy) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{2x}{2xy^3} = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

$$F = \int \frac{1}{y^3} (y^4) dx + \frac{x^2}{y^2} + \int \frac{1}{y^3} (2y^2) dy + c$$

$$F = xy + \frac{x^2}{y^2} + 2 \ln|y|$$

The old solution

$$M = y^4 + 2xy \text{ and } \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} = 4y^3 + 2x$$

$$N = xy^3 + 2y^2 - 2x^2 \text{ and } \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} = y^3 - 4x$$

$$\frac{1}{M} \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{1}{y(y^3 + 2x)} (y^3 - 4x - 4y^3 - 2x) = \frac{-3}{y} \text{ then I.F.} = e^{\int \frac{-3dy}{y}} = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

➤ **Example 4**

Solve $(3y+4xy^2)dx + (2x + 3x^2y)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{3y}{2x} \text{ then } f(x,y) = x^3y^2 \text{ without integration}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{4xy^2}{3x^2y} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{3y}{2x} \text{ and } g(x,y) = x^4y^3 \text{ without integration}$$

$$F(x,y) = f(x,y)+g(x,y) = x^3y^2 + x^4y^3 = x^3y^2(1 + xy) + c \text{ without integration End .}$$

Another solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{3y}{2x} \text{ then } f(x,y) = x^3y^2$$

$$\text{Then } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{x^3y^2}{\partial y} = 2x^3y = \mu(2x) \text{ so } \mu = x^2y$$

$$F = x^3y^2 + \int x^2y(4xy^2)dx = x^3y^2 + x^4y^3 = x^3y^2(1 + xy) + c \quad \text{End}$$

The old method of solution

$$\text{I.F.} = \frac{1}{xM - yN} = \frac{1}{xy + x^2y^2} \text{ where } xy + x^2y^2 \neq 0$$

➤ **Example 5**

Solve $(y^4 + 2y)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^4 - 4x)dy = 0$

Solution

$$(y^4 + 2y)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^4 - 4x)dy = 0$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

$$.y(y^3 + 2)dx + (xy^3 + 2y^4 - 4x)dy = 0$$

$$\text{So } \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^4}{xy^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{x} \text{ then } f=xy$$

$$\frac{\partial(xy)}{\partial y} = x \text{ so } x = \mu(xy^3) \text{ then } \mu = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

$$F(x,y) = f(x,y) + \int \frac{1}{y^3} (2y)dx + \int_{(y \text{ only})} \frac{1}{y^3} (2y^4)dy = xy + \frac{2x}{y^2} + y^2 = c \text{ End}$$

The old solution

$$\frac{1}{M} \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{-3}{y} \text{ then I.F.} = e^{\int \frac{-3dy}{y}} = \frac{1}{y^3}$$

➤ **Example 6**

Solve $(x^2 + y^2 + 2x)dx + 2ydy = 0$

Solution

$$(x^2 + y^2 + 2x)dx + 2ydy = 0$$

Since $M = x^2 + y^2 + 2x$ which contains 3 terms and $N = 2y$ which contains 1 term and there is a common derivative between them so we expect that $\mu = e^x$.

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^2}{2y} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{2} \text{ then } f(x,y) = y^2e^{\int dx} = y^2e^x$$

$$\frac{\partial f(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(y^2e^x)}{\partial y} = 2ye^x \text{ then } 2ye^x = \mu(2y) \text{ so } \mu = e^x$$

$$F(x,y) = y^2 e^x + \int e^x(x^2 + 2x)dx = e^x(y^2 + x^2) + c \text{ End}$$

The old way of the solution is

$$\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = 1 \text{ sol. } F. = e^{\int 1dx} = e^x$$

➤ **Example 7**

Solve $(-2y+x^2y^3)dx - (2x + 2x^3)dy = 0$

Solution

$$(-2y+x^2y^3)dx + (-2x - 2x^3)dy = 0$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{x^3y^3}$$

$$(-2y+x^2y^3)dx + (-2x - 2x^3)dy = 0$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2y}{-2x} \text{ then } f(x,y) = x^{-2}y^{-2} = \frac{1}{x^2y^2}$$

$$\frac{\partial f(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \frac{1}{x^2y^2} = \frac{-2}{x^2y^3} \text{ then } \frac{-2}{x^2y^3} = \mu(-2x) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{x^3y^3}$$

$$F(x,y) = \frac{1}{x^2y^2} + \int \frac{1}{x^3y^3} (x^2y^3)dx + \int_{(y \text{ only})} \frac{1}{x^3y^3} (-2x^3)dy = \frac{1}{x^2y^2} + \ln|x| + \frac{1}{y^2} + c \text{ End .}$$

Another solution

$$(-2y+x^2y^3)dx + (-2x - 2x^3)dy = 0$$

Then

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{x^2y^3}{-2x^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^3}{-2x} \rightarrow \frac{-2dy}{y^3} + \frac{dx}{x} \rightarrow \int \frac{-2dy}{y^3} + \int \frac{dx}{x} = \frac{1}{y^2} + \ln|x|$$

$$F = \frac{1}{x^2y^2} + \frac{1}{y^2} + \ln|x| + c \text{ End}$$

The old solution is

$$I.F. = x^\alpha y^\beta$$

➤ **Example 8**

Solve $y(8x-9y)dx+2x(x-3y)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{8xy}{2x^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{8y}{2x} = 2\left(\frac{4y}{x}\right) \text{ then } f(x,y) = 2x^4y \text{ [without integration]}$$

$$\frac{\partial(2x^4y)}{\partial y} = 2x^4 = \mu(2x^2) \text{ then } \mu = x^2$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-9y^2}{-6xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} - 3\left(\frac{3y}{2x}\right) \text{ so } g(x,y) = -3x^3y^2 \text{ [without integration]}$$

$$F(x,y) = 2x^4y - 3x^3y^2 = xy(2x^3 - 3x^2) + c \text{ [without integration]}$$

$$\text{Also } \frac{\partial(-3x^3y^2)}{\partial y} = -6x^3y = \mu(-6xy) \text{ then } \mu = x^2$$

$$\mu = x^2$$

The old solution is

$$I.F. = x^\alpha y^\beta$$

➤ **Example 9**

Solve $-y(y+x)dx+(xy+x^2)dy = 0$

Solution

Homogeneous and its power is (2) so multiply the D.E. by (2)

$$-2y(y+x)dx+ 2(xy+x^2)dy = 0$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2y^2}{2xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2y}{2x} \quad \text{so } f(x,y) = \frac{y^2}{x^2} \text{ without integration}$$

$$\frac{\partial f(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(\frac{y^2}{x^2})}{\partial y} = \frac{2y}{x^2} \text{ so } \frac{2y}{x^2} = \mu(2xy) \text{ then } \mu = \frac{1}{x^3} \text{ i.e. not exact}$$

$$F(x,y) = \frac{y^2}{x^2} + \int \frac{1}{x^3}(-xy)dx = \frac{y^2}{2x^2} + \frac{y}{x} = c \quad \text{End.}$$

The same results we can obtain if

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2xy}{2x^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2y}{2x} \quad \text{and } g(x,y) = \frac{y^2}{x^2} \text{ without integration}$$

$$\frac{\partial g(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial(\frac{y^2}{x^2})}{\partial y} = \frac{2y}{x^2} \text{ so } \frac{2y}{x^2} = \mu(2xy) \text{ then } \mu = \frac{1}{x^3}$$

$$F(x,y) = \int \frac{1}{x^3}(-xy)dx + \frac{y^2}{x^2} = \frac{y}{x} + \frac{y^2}{x^2} = c \quad \text{End}$$

The old solution is

$$\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{-3}{x}$$

➤ **Example 10**

Solve $y(x^3 - y)dx - x(x^3 + y)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y^2}{-xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{-x} \quad \text{then } g(x,y) = \frac{1}{xy}$$

$$\frac{\partial g(x,y)}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \frac{1}{xy}}{\partial x} = \frac{-1}{x^2y} = \mu(-y^2) \quad \text{then } \mu = \frac{1}{x^2y^3}$$

$$F(x,y) = \frac{1}{xy} + \int \frac{1}{x^2y^3}(x^3y)dx = \frac{1}{xy} + \frac{x^2}{2y^2} = c$$

$$x^3 + 2y = cxy^2 \quad \text{End}$$

the old solution is by inspection

➤ **Example 11**

A – solve $-(3y^4 + x^3y)dx + (3xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$

B – solve $-(y^4 + x^3y)dx + (xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$

Solution A

$$(-3y^4 - x^3y)dx + (3xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y^4}{3xy^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y}{3x} \quad \text{then } f(x,y) = x^{-3}y^3 = \frac{y^3}{x^3} \text{ without integration}$$

$$\frac{\partial f(x,y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \frac{y^3}{x^3}}{\partial y} = \frac{3y^2}{x^3} \text{ so } \frac{3y^2}{x^3} = \mu(3xy^3) \quad \text{then } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4y}$$

$$F(x,y) = \frac{y^3}{x^3} + \int \frac{1}{x^4y}(-x^3y)dx + \int_{\text{y only}} \frac{1}{x^4y}(x^4)dy = \frac{y^3}{x^3} - \ln|x| + \ln|y| + c$$

Another solution

$$(-3y^4 - x^3y)dx + (3xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$$

Solution

$$(y^4 - x^3y)dx + (3xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$$

$$\text{so } y(y^3 - x^3)dx + (3xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0 \quad \text{i.e. } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4y}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-x^3}{x^4} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{x} \text{ so } \frac{dy}{y} - \frac{dx}{x} \rightarrow \ln y - \ln x \text{ then } g = \ln \frac{y}{x}$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \ln \frac{y}{x}}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{y} = \mu(x^4) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4 y}$$

$$F = \frac{y^3}{x^3} - \ln|x| + \ln|y| + c \text{ [without integration]}$$

Solution (B)

$$-(y^4 + x^3y)dx + (xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$$

Then $-y(y^3 + x^3)dx + (xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-x^3y}{x^4} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{x} \text{ so } \frac{dy}{y} - \frac{dx}{x} \rightarrow g(x,y) = \ln y - \ln x \text{ [without integration]} \frac{\partial g}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \ln \frac{y}{x}}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{y} = \mu(x^4) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4 y}$$

note ; $\mu = \frac{1}{x^4 y}$ (y outside M and x^4 is inside N)

$$F(x,y) = \frac{1}{x^4 y} \int -y^4 dx - \ln x + \ln y + c = \frac{y^3}{3x^3} - \ln|x| + \ln|y| + c \text{ End .}$$

Another solution

$$-(y^4 + x^3y)dx + (xy^3 + x^4)dy = 0 \rightarrow -y(y^3 + x^3)dx + x(y^3 + x^3)dy = 0$$

We see that there is homogeneous D.E. inside the brackets of power 3

So multiply it by 3

$$-3(y^4 + x^3y)dx + 3(xy^3 + x^4)dy$$

$$\text{Then } \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y^4}{3xy^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-3y}{3x} \rightarrow f = \frac{y^3}{x^3} \text{ so } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial (\frac{y^3}{x^3})}{\partial y} = \frac{3y^2}{x^3} = \mu(3xy^3)$$

$$\text{So } \mu = \frac{1}{x^4 y}$$

$$F = \frac{y^3}{x^3} - \int \frac{1}{x^4 y} (3x^3 y) dx + \int \frac{1}{x^4 y} (3x^4) dy + c = \frac{y^3}{x^3} - 3 \ln|x| + 3 \ln|y| + c \text{ END}$$

The old solution is

$$\text{Let } y = vx \text{ so } dy = v dx + x dv$$

➤ **Example 12**

Solve

$$(3x^2 + y^2)dx + (2xy + x^3 + xy^2 - y)dy = 0$$

Solution

Since there are (2) parameters in M(x,y) and (4) in N(x,y) so we expect that I.F. is equal (e^y)

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{3x^2}{x^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{(3)}{x} \text{ so } f(x,y) = x^3 e^{\int dy} = x^3 e^y$$

$$\frac{\partial (x^3 e^y)}{\partial y} = x^3 e^y \text{ then } x^3 e^y = \mu(x^3) \text{ so } \mu = e^y$$

$$F(x,y) = x^3 e^y + \int y^2 e^y dx + \int e^y (-y) dy = e^y (x^3 + xy^2 - y + 1) = c \text{ End .}$$

The old solution

$$\frac{1}{M} \left(\frac{\partial N}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial M}{\partial y} \right) = 1 \text{ sol. } F. = e^{\int 1 dy} = e^y$$

➤ **Example 13**

Solve $(x^2 + y^2 + x)dx + xy dy = 0$

Solution

Semi homogeneous because $d(xy) = xdy + ydx$ which are not found in the D.E. so multiply by 2 then $2(x^2 + y^2 + x)dx + 2xy dy = 0$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y^2}{2xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{2x} \text{ so } f = x^2y^2$$

$$\frac{\partial(x^2y^2)}{\partial y} = 2x^2y \text{ then } 2x^2y = \mu(2xy) \text{ so } \mu = x$$

$$F(x,y) = x^2y^2 + \int x(x^2 + x)dx = x^2y^2 + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^3}{3} + c \text{ End.}$$

The old solution

$$\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{1}{x} \text{ sol. } F. = e^{\int \frac{1dx}{x}} = x$$

➤ Example 14

Solve $(3x^2 + y^2 + 4)dx + x(x - 2y)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y^2}{-2xy} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{-2x} \text{ so } g = \frac{-y^2}{x} \text{ then } \frac{\partial g}{\partial y} = \frac{-2y}{x} = \mu(-2xy) \text{ so } \mu = \frac{1}{x^2}$$

$$F = \frac{-y^2}{x} + \int \frac{1}{x^2} (3x^2 + 4)dx + \int \frac{x^2}{x^2} dy + c = \frac{-y^2}{x} + 3x + y - \frac{4}{x} + c \text{ End}$$

The old solution is

$$\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{-2}{x} \text{ sol. } F. = e^{\int \frac{-2dx}{x}} = e^{-2\ln x} = \frac{1}{x^2}$$

➤ Example 15

Solve $y(xy+2)dx + (\frac{5x^2y}{2} + 8x - 4)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{xy^2}{\frac{5x^2y}{2}} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y}{5x} \text{ so } f = x^2y^5 \text{ then } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = 5x^2y^4 = \mu \left(\frac{5x^2y}{2} \right) \text{ so } \mu = 2y^3$$

$$F = x^2y^5 + \int 2y^3(2y)dx - \int 2y^3(4y^2)dy + c = x^2y^5 + 4xy^4 - 2y^4 + c \text{ END}$$

The old solution is $F. = x^\alpha y^\beta$

➤ Example 16

Solve $(5x^4 - 2x^2y + 2y^2 - 4xy)dx - 2(x^2 - 2y)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-2x^2y}{-2x^2} \rightarrow f = -2x^2ye^x \text{ then } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = -2x^2e^x = \mu(-2x^2) \text{ so } \mu = e^x$$

$$F = \int e^x(5x^4 - 2x^2y + 2y^2 - 4xy)dx + c$$

The old solution is

$$I. F. = x^\alpha y^\beta$$

➤ Example 17

solve $(xy - 4\ln x + x^2 \sin x^2)dx + x^2dy = 0$

solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{xy}{x^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{y}{x} \rightarrow f = xy \text{ so } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = x = \mu(x^2) \text{ then } \mu = \frac{1}{x}$$

$$F = xy + \int \frac{1}{x} (-4\ln x + x^2 \sin x^2)dx = xy - 2(\ln x)^2 - \frac{\cos x^2}{2} + c$$

The old solution is

$$\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{-1}{x} \text{ and } I.F. = \frac{1}{x}$$

➤ Example 18

Solve $y(1 - xy)dx + x(xy - 1)dy = 0$

Solution

Since we have $yf_1(xy) + xf_2(xy) = 0$ then we can multiply the D.E. by (-1)

$$-y(1 - xy)dx - x(xy - 1)dy = 0 \text{ so } \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{-x} \text{ then } f = \frac{-1}{xy} \text{ and } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{xy^2} = \mu(x)$$

$$so\mu = \frac{1}{x^2y^2}$$

$$F = \frac{-1}{xy} - \int \frac{1}{x^2y^2}(xy^2)dx + \int \frac{1}{x^2y^2}(x^2y)dy + c = \frac{-1}{xy} - \ln x + \ln y + c \text{ END}$$

The old solution is

$$I.F. = \frac{1}{Mx+Ny} = \frac{1}{xy(1-xy-xy+1)} = \frac{1}{2x^2y^2}$$

➤ **Example 19**

Solve $(2y^4 - 2x^3y)dx - (4xy^3 - x^4)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{2y^4}{-4xy^3} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + 2\frac{y}{-2x} \rightarrow f = -2\frac{y^2}{x} \text{ then } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{-4y}{x} = \mu(-4xy^3)$$

$$\mu = \frac{1}{x^2y^2}$$

$$F = \int \frac{1}{x^2y^2}(2y^4 - 2x^3y)dx + C = -2\frac{y^2}{x} - \frac{x^2}{y} + C \text{ END}$$

The old solution is

$$I.F. = \frac{1}{Mx+Ny} = \frac{1}{xy(2y^3-2x^3-4y^3+x^3)} = \frac{1}{-(2xy^4+x^4y)}$$

➤ **Example 20**

solve $(-y^3 + x^2y)dx + (xy^2 - x^3)dy = 0$

Solution

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y^3}{xy^2} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} + \frac{-y}{x} \rightarrow f = \frac{y}{x} \text{ so } \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} = \frac{1}{x} = \mu(xy^2) \text{ then } \mu = \frac{1}{x^2y^2}$$

$$F = \frac{y}{x} + \int \frac{1}{x^2y^2}(x^2y)dx + c = \frac{y}{x} + \frac{x}{y} + c \text{ solution}$$

II. CONCLUSIONS

- The new methods are innovative and by them we facilitate the solutions of the problems either by finding the answers directly i.e. without integration or by finding the integrating factor directly or simply.
- I see that these methods can be new subjects of the CALCULUS book.
- I see that these methods can share in the Intelligent Artificial (AI) because of the short time, less papers and efforts (may be decrease the human mistakes).

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